

Data-Driven Model For Heat Load Prediction In Buildings Connected To District Heating Networks

Alaeddine Hajri
Department of Computer Systems Engineering
Mediterranean Institute of Technology
Tunis, Tunisia
alaeddine.hajri94@gmail.com

Ana M. Macarulla
Institute of Technology, Faculty of Engineering
University of Deusto
Avda. Universidades, 24, Bilbao 48007, Spain
ORCID: 0000-0001-8741-0990

Roberto Garay-Marinez
Institute of Technology, Faculty of Engineering
University of Deusto
Avda. Universidades, 24, Bilbao 48007, Spain
ORCID: 0000-0003-2331-6561

Mohamed Amin Ben Sassi
Department of Computer Systems Engineering
Mediterranean Institute of Technology
Tunis, Tunisia
mohamed.bensassi@medtech.tn

Abstract—In this study we investigate the heat load patterns in one building using multi-step forecasting model. We combine the Autoregressive models that use multiple eXogenous variables (ARX) with Seasonally adaptable Time of Week and Climate dependent models (S-TOW-C), to obtain a robust and accurate regression model that we called S-TOW-C-ARX used in time series forecasting. Based on the experiment results, it has been shown that the proposed model is suitable for short term heat load forecasting. The best forecasting performance is achieved in winter term where the prediction values are from 4 to 20 % away from the targets, which are commonly seen as very good values.

Keywords— *Data-driven model, Short-term load forecasting, Energy in Buildings*

I. Introduction

Thermal energy uses in buildings form a large part of global energy demand. 50% of Europe's total gross final energy consumption are destined for heating and cooling. According to [1], where the lion's part (79%) corresponds to heating and domestic hot water production at household level.

In large buildings, heating systems are typically centralized. Also, in many cities, District Heating (DH) systems are used to deliver heat to large sections of the cities. Unlike boilers and heat pumps, DH can use a wide variety of energy sources, including renewable energy uses as well as fossil fuels.

Finding an overall balanced approach to deal with the robust design of heating systems, along with their efficiency, is one of the central dilemmas for building engineers. In this context, these systems are sized to meet the peak demand rather than focusing on their optimal efficiency.

The control for supply temperature of buildings as well as DH networks can improve the efficiency of these systems [2]. Usually, these controls are static and rule-based, they are commonly based on simplified thermostatic rules. These rules could be optimized through a suitable adaptation based on the evolution of the heat demand in the coming hours. Even basic temperature optimization has led to reductions of 4.8% of distribution loss in real life cases [3].

Our study will focus on how to characterize and forecast the heating demand to ensure the effective operation of large buildings systems. For doing so, we use data driven modelling approach, where the consideration of physical background of the building is not required. So-called black box modelling is

a fast and efficient way of creating load models [4]. By using data-driven approaches, it becomes possible to make improvements and adjustments over time by allowing for adaptation and updating of the model based on new data.

In this regard, several studies have been carried out using these approaches. A data driven model based on present and recent history of weather data was proposed in [5]. This type of model, so called AutoRegressive with eXogenous variables (ARX), was found optimal with a 4-hour historical values. The model was tested against synthetic data of a building energy simulation, with forecasting error lower than 4% in winter term.

A Time-of-Week (ToW) Segmented Multiple Linear Regression (MLR) model considering several climatic variables was developed in [6], which delivered overall fine performance at an aggregated level, but failed at replicating intra daily patterns. Potentially due to its lack of history.

A seasonal autoregressive integrated moving average (SARIMA) process was proposed in [7] for modelling the system heat load. Although suitable to replicate yearly patterns, this model lacks the capacity to adapt to variations in present weather conditions, as it lacks exogenous climatic variables that may have an impact on the heat load.

Several works [6, 8, 9] have showed the relevance of calendar and social data in the modelling of heat loads in buildings. Three different machine learning models, namely ordinary least square (OLS), support vector regression (SVR) and multilayer perceptron model (MPR) are proposed in [10] to investigate the inclusion of calendar data and holiday data for forecasting the aggregated heat load of the DH system of Aarhus, Denmark. The SVR show the best performance with an MAPE of 6.4%, nevertheless, the inclusion of local holiday showed a minor overall improvement. This indicates the limited interpretability of the proposed model.

In this study, we introduce an AutoRegressive model with Multiple eXogenous variables. We also incorporate Time of the Week (ToW) variables as eXogenous variables. By doing so, we believe that it allows to incorporate ToW sensitivity over an otherwise stable ARX model, and we avoid the need for segmentation. This is a mixture of the approaches in the above-mentioned [5, 6] leading to a potentially interesting application. Based on a common approach, we develop various adaptations for specific periods of the year. Ultimately, the model can model the unknown with a minimum number of parameters, achieving substantial

simplification of linear prediction and providing an effective linear model of stationary time series.

II. METHODOLOGY

We follow a 4-step methodology: (1) Data sources (2) Outlier detection and data imputation. (3) Model definition. (4) Model calibration.

A. Data Sources

Two sources of data are used: Heat load (1) and Weather (2) data. We take heat load data from a district heating sub-network with 42 substations (buildings), located in Tartu (Estonia). In each building, a heat meter provides hourly values of heat load (along with other variables). Climate data is taken from the meteorological station at the university of Tartu [11-14]. Data for a full year (2019) is used.

Data analysis in figure 2 shows a great correlation between heat load and climate. Heat load increases with decreasing temperature. Part of the heating load is related to Domestic Hot Water consumption (DHW) which known to be temperature and season independent and is illustrated by the roughly horizontal load profile at higher temperature levels.

Multiple seasonality is observed, where the weekly patterns reflect the variation in heat load on weekdays versus weekends.

B. Outlier Detection and Data Imputation

Outliers have been detected and removed based on statistical significance tests. Considering the sensitivity of data to climate, the process was conducted individually for temperature-homogeneous areas at intervals of 2.5°C. Anomalies were identified using the Inter Quartile Rule (IQR) for each subset of temperature.

Observation lying above the third quartile + 1.5*IQR and lying below the first quartile - 1.5*IQR are considered outliers. Where IQR is defined as the distance between the first and third quartiles.

Based on this criterion, a total of 8.42% of the data points were identified as outliers.

C. Model Definition

We propose a Seasonally-adaptable, Time Of Week and Climate dependent Auto Regressive Model (S-TOW-C-ARX). The model adapts through discrete deviations of the load for specific TOW values. The linear regression function is performed to identify the coefficients, where the heat load output value is considered in previous timesteps. The model components are presented in the following equation:

$$L_i = c + \sum(a_{na} \times L_{i-na}) + \sum(b_{nb} \times T_{i-nb}) + \sum(c_{nc} \times I_{i-nc}) + \sum(e_{nd} \times bool_CD) \quad (1)$$

Where a_{na} are the autoregressive parameter, b_{nb} , c_{nc} are the exogenous parameters corresponding to Temperature and Solar Irradiation respectively, and e_{nd} are the parameter related to calendar data. The L_i refers to the heat load at time t (hours), L_{i-na} , T_{i-nb} and I_{i-nc} represent the present and lagged heat load, temperature and irradiation flux variables respectively. The calendar data are symbolized as $bool_CD$ which represent each hour of the week separately.

Fig. 1. Heat load vs outdoor temperature in Building 10259: Shoulder period (a) with Weekly Consumption (04-03-2019 to 10-03-2019) (b)

D. Model Calibration

The dataset was split into training and testing sets. The splitting process was performed in a way that the learning data and testing data coincide with all different heat consumption patterns with the respect to the season of the year. The training data have been defined containing odd days whereas the testing set have been defined containing even days.

Individual datasets were separated for winter (December to February) and shoulder (March - May + September - November) periods. Data from the summer was not considered relevant due to its low load values. Furthermore, individual datasets were created for workdays and weekends.

1) Statistical Significance and Feature Selection

Models were fitted to the ordinary least square regression (OLS). Thereafter feature selection was conducted using variance threshold. The selection procedure was based on p-value threshold in which the entry criterion was set to a value lower than 0.05.

This procedure was complemented with visual checks of the accuracy of the models after the feature selection to ensure that our assumptions and feature selections were reasonable

2) Model Optimization and Data Scenarios

The models are built with different available explanatory variables, so that the need of each input variable to predict the output was assessed. This was done under three different types of data scenarios. Table 1 displays the Scenarios where several variables are added to the models based on an iterative process using forward selection method. In each model, optimal input parameters are selected to achieve the best performance of prediction accuracy of heat load.

3) Model Assessment Criteria

Modelling accuracy is tested with training and testing datasets.

Training data is used to measure model accuracy on heat load characterization. In this context, we have checked the goodness of fit for each model with the calculation of R-squared value and F-statistic. Furthermore, a graphical visual inspection of residual analysis is conducted.

Testing data is used to measure model accuracy in heat load prediction. The selection of optimal input parameters is evaluated using different evaluation metrics such as the Akaike information criterion (AIC), Bayesian information criterion (BIC) and Adjusted R-squared.

The models with their data scenarios are scored according to hourly mean absolute error (MAE), root mean square error (RMSE) and mean absolute percentage error (MAPE).

III. Results and Discussion

A. Model Evaluation to Characterize the Heat Load

1) OLS Goodness of Fit

As shown in table II, the shoulder season models yield an excellent fit to the observed data. For workdays models 88% of the variability observed in the heat load variable is explained by the regression model. The minimum value of R-squared is shown in the winter term, essentially for weekends model where 76 % of the variability observed in the heat load variable is explained by the regression model.

The models of the shoulder term displayed the higher F-statistic values. For the prob (F statistic) we could see that all the values were exceedingly small numbers. For that reason, the null hypothesis of the models was rejected.

2) Residual Analysis

Figure 2 present the heat load predicted values against the observed values of workdays and weekends models in winter and shoulder terms. Both cases, there is a ~5kWh accuracy, which impacts on lower relative accuracy for lower load periods (shoulder period)

B. Model Evaluation to Predict the Heat Load

1) Model Comparison and Selection

From figure 3, we observe some variation between the magnitude of the mean absolute error (MAE) and the root mean square errors (RMSE).

Models improve when adding explanatory variables such as lagged weather variables and calendar data.

Given that loads are higher in winter, models also present greater RMSE and MAE values for those periods in all the three data scenarios. This is particularly so for weekends.

The remaining of this paper is focused at optimizing models with all the available explanatory variables. Table 3 represents the models for this scenario which include significant calendar data inputs.

The workdays model in winter term is denoted by Q3_T1_I1 (TUE_1h_WED_3,7h_MON_8h), that corresponds to the following:

- Q3 represents the heat load with three lagged values
- T1, I1 represent the lagged values at 1-hour historical data for temperature and irradiation flux respectively
- WED_3,7h refers to the significant predictors of hours at 03:00 and 7:00 on Wednesday

- MON_8h refers to the significant predictors of hours 08:00 on Monday.

TABLE I. MODELS WITH DIFFERENT DATA SCENARIOS.

	12 historical values of Power	Present Temperature	24 historical values of Temperature	Present Irradiation	24 historical values of Irradiation	Calendar Data
lagged heat load data	✓					
lagged weather data (Temperature)	✓	✓	✓			
lagged weather data (Irradiation flux)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
calendar data	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

TABLE II. SUMMARY STATISTICS WITH SIGNIFICANT PARAMETERS

	Winter Term		Shoulder Term	
	Workdays	Weekends	Workdays	Weekends
R-Squared	0.845	0.763	0.883	0.866
F-statistic	342.7	76.03	707	359.7
Prob (F-statistic)	8.52e-296	5.68e-80	0.00	1.17e-258

Fig. 2. Examining the predicted heat load against actual heat load in winter (left) and shoulder (right) periods

Fig. 3. Root mean square error (RMSE) and mean absolute error (MAE) of the four forecast models (workdays-winter, weekends-winter, workdays-shoulder and weekends-shoulder) for each data scenario

The same notation was used for the models for winter weekends, shoulder period workdays and weekends (Q1_T1_I1 (SAT_2,10h_SUN_1,4,5h); Q3_T2_I2 (THU_2h_FRI_7,10,11,21h_MON_0,1,8h); and Q3_T1_I1 (SAT_22h_SUN_15,16,18,19,22h) respectively).

Figure 4 provides an outlook of hourly RMSE and MAE values for selected periods. We can see that these values appear to be large in winter term compared to shoulder months. In this context the evaluation metrics are large in the evening hours, this could be explained by the large heat load with large variance during the winter months. This is particularly so in January, where RMSE and MAE values over 3- 4 kW are common in some hours. These values are lower for shoulder periods.

In the same figure, also the MAPE is presented, in this case, it is lower for winter periods than shoulder periods, as the prediction errors are proportionally smaller compared to the heat load in winter periods. MAPE values in the range of 4 to 20 % are observed in winter, while these values rise to 20 to 80 % in shoulder periods.

Figure 5 presents the histograms for the hourly errors for each month. The 10% and 90% quantiles are specified. It can be seen that most forecasting residuals are bound to the ± 2.5 kW range.

In figure 6 a summary of the errors is presented. With some variations, it can be seen that MAE and RMSE values are bounded to 0.5kW and 2.5kW respectively, and that the 10-90 inter quartile ranges are -4 to 4kW.

As a result of all these metrics, no bias is observed in our model.

IV. CONCLUSION

We have presented a data driven model for the characterization and prediction of heat demand in buildings connected to district heating (DH) networks. Our new model is applied in a short-term heat load forecast with high temporal resolution (hourly and daily timestamp) for different buildings relying on weather and calendar information.

Statistically, the mean absolute percentage error (MAPE) is ranging between 4 to 20 % in winter term, which is considered as an indication that the forecast is acceptably accurate. Whereas, in shoulder term the MAPE is ranging between 20 to 80% which is considered as an indication that the forecast is low. The models in winter and shoulder term show a good performance in predicting the heat demand in early morning of the days. Having such estimation available for different buildings in district heating networks help to optimize the resource for heat generation and give rise to both energy and economic savings.

In operational forecast systems, a model with simple and reliable data input may work to make a more robust system. Having several features are not always an advantage to improve the accuracy. Nevertheless, future works should inspect different types of models to simplify the feature selection procedure and handle multiple inputs variables with noisy dependencies. Hence, make the forecasting process more applicable to a wide range of district heating systems around the world.

TABLE III. EQUATIONS OF THE MODELS THAT INCLUDE SIGNIFICANT CALENDAR DATA INPUTS (3RD DATA SCENARIO)

Winter. Workday	$Q = C_0 + C_{Q1} \times Q_1 + C_{Q2} \times Q_2 + C_{Q3} \times Q_3 + C_{T0} \times T_0 + C_{T1} \times T_1 + C_{I0} \times I_0 + C_{I1} \times I_1 + w_i + TUE_{1h} + WED_{3h} + WED_{7h} + MON_{8h}$
Winter. Weekend	$Q = C_0 + C_{Q1} \times Q_1 + C_{T0} \times T_0 + C_{T1} \times T_1 + C_{I0} \times I_0 + C_{I1} \times I_1 + w_i + SAT_{2h} + SAT_{10h} + SUN_{1h} + SUN_{4h} + SUN_{5h}$
Shoulder. Workday	$Q = C_0 + C_{Q1} \times Q_1 + C_{Q2} \times Q_2 + C_{Q3} \times Q_3 + C_{T0} \times T_0 + C_{T1} \times T_1 + C_{T2} \times T_2 + C_{I0} \times I_0 + C_{I1} \times I_1 + C_{I2} \times I_2 + w_i + THU_{2h} + FRI_{7h} + FRI_{10h} + FRI_{11h} + FRI_{21h} + MON_{0h} + MON_{1h} + MON_{8h}$
Shoulder. Weekend	$Q = C_0 + C_{Q1} \times Q_1 + C_{Q2} \times Q_2 + C_{Q3} \times Q_3 + C_{T0} \times T_0 + C_{T1} \times T_1 + C_{I0} \times I_0 + C_{I1} \times I_1 + w_i + SAT_{22h} + SUN_{15h} + SUN_{16h} + SUN_{18h} + SUN_{19h} + SUN_{22h}$

Fig. 4. Examining the performance of the four models for February (a), January (b), May (c), October (d), where the forecast error varies with time of the days.

Fig. 5. Forecast error histograms of the four models. The forecast error distribution is shown for February (a), January (b), November (c), October (d) in the year along with 10% and 90% quantiles. The forecast is too high when having a positive error, and too low when having negative error

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This study has been carried out in the context of the ATELIER project. This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 864374.

The research leading to this study received funding from the Basque Government grant for Research Groups, "Grupos de investigación del Sistema Universitario Vasco, Departamento de Educación, Universidades e Investigación" (Research group: IT1677-22).

Fig. 6. Model error metrics. RMSE & Mean Error (a) and 10-90% IQR range (b)

REFERENCES

- [1] Eurostat. (2020). Energy consumption in households
- [2] G. Mbiydzeyuy, S. Nowaczyk, H. Knutsson, D. Vanhoudt, J. Brage, E. Calikus, "Opportunities for Machine Learning in District Heating". Applied science, 2021
- [3] O. Eguarte, A. Marijuan, R. Garay, M. Raud, I. Hagu, "Data-driven assessment for the supervision of District Heating Networks," ICACER 2022, Barcelona, 2022,
- [4] G. Steindl, Ch. Pfeiffer, "Comparison of Black Box Models for Load Profile Generation of District Heating Networks", SDEWES 2017, Dubrovnik, 2017
- [5] G. Eguizabal, R. Garay, I. Flores, "Simplified model for the short-term forecasting of heat loads in buildings", ICACER 2021, Barcelona, 2021
- [6] M. Lumbreras, R. Garay, B. Arregi, "Data driven model for heat load prediction in buildings connected to District Heating by using smart heat meters". Energy, 2021
- [7] G. Grosswindhager, A. Voigt, "Online Short-Term Forecast of System Heat Load in District Heating Networks". 2011
- [8] M. Lumbreras, G. Diarce, K. Martin, R. Garay, B. Arregi, "Unsupervised recognition and prediction of daily patterns in heating loads in buildings", Journal of Building Engineering, 2023
- [9] S. Zhan, Z. Liu, A. Chong, D. Yan, "Building categorization revisited: A clustering-based approach to using smart meter data for building energy benchmarking". Applied Energy, 2020
- [10] M. Dahl, A. Brun, O. Kirsebom, G.A. Andresen, "Improving Short-Term Heat Load Forecasts with Calendar and Holiday Data". Energies 2018
- [11] University of Tartu weather station. <https://meteo.physic.ut.ee> (accessed, 2022)
- [12] A. Garrido, O. Eguarte, R. Garay, M. Raud, I. Hagu, "Lessons Learnt from Substation Inspection on Low Temperature District Heating Networks". environmental sciences proceedings, 2021
- [13] M. Lumbreras, G. Diarce, K. Martin, R. Garay, B. Arregi, "Unsupervised recognition and prediction of daily patterns in heating loads in buildings". Journal of Building Engineering, 2022
- [14] M. Lumbreras, R. Garay, A. Marijuan, "Energy meters in District-Heating Substations for Heat Consumption Characterization and Prediction Using Machine-Learning Techniques" IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science, 2020

